

**ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К АНАЛИЗУ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКОЙ КАУЗАТИВИЗАЦИИ В
УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ**

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**PRAGMATIC APPROACH TO THE ANALYSIS OF GRAMMATICAL CAUSATIVIZATION IN THE
UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES**

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Аннотация

В данной статье в результате прагматического подхода к анализу грамматико-лингвистического явления каузативизации авторы демонстрируют различные каузальные значения, выражаемые одной и той же формой, в зависимости от контекста и ситуации, в которой происходит общение между собеседниками. Кроме того, авторы проводят различие между истинным и псевдопричинным употреблением одного и того же грамматического шаблона в зависимости от определения, данного грамматической причинности в этой статье.

Abstract

In this article at the result of the pragmatic approach to the analysis of the grammatical linguistic phenomenon causativization the authors demonstrate different causal meanings expressed by one and the same form depended on the context and the situation in which the communication takes place among interlocutors. Besides, the authors distinguish between true causative and pseudo-causative usage of the same grammatical pattern depended on the definition given to the grammatical causation in this article.

Ключевые слова: переходность/непереходимость, каузативизация/некаузативизация, агглютинативные, флективные, относительные аффиксы, производные аффиксы, корневые морфемы, аффиксальные морфемы, нулевые морфемы, аналитическая, синтетическая, синтагматическая и парадигматическая оппозиция, бинарная оппозиция, фактивная причинность, пермиссивная причинность.

Keywords: transitivity/intransitivity, causativization/non-causativization, agglutinative, inflected, relative affixes, derivative affixes, root morphemes, affixal morphemes, zero morphemes, analytically, synthetically, syntagmatic and paradigmatic opposition, binary opposition, factitive causation, permissive causation.

In linguistics discourse “pragmatics” refers to the strategies by the help of which language users relate the lexical or grammar meaning of utterances to their communicative value in context. Pragmatic approach includes semantic meanings of words and structures found in dictionaries and grammars, and the “pragmatic” values which these linguistic elements receive when they are used in communication. Communicative

competence involves not only dictionary or grammar meaning, but also the meanings expressed in the course of communication. Grammatical structures have not only grammatical forms, but they also have different meanings in context, proceeding from the position they are used. The term meaning subsumes lexical, semantic and pragmatic meaning. Here we take into consideration form, meaning and function. Focusing on form we

take into account the level of integration of the speaker's attitude to all three aspects: form, meaning and function. Although the term "pragmatics" relates to the study of "how we do things with language" it is reasonable to identify **when, where, how and why** the analyzed linguistic phenomenon is used, proceeding from the situation and the context it is used. So the aim of the article is the pragmatic approach to the analysis of the grammatical linguistic phenomenon causativization in the languages of different genealogical families: English (Germanic) and Uzbek (Turkic).

In linguistics causative meaning is the operation where the subject causes someone or something to do something or causes a change in state of a non-volitional event, sometimes the subject lets the caused object do something the latter is inclined to do. As the aim of the article is to demonstrate the pragmatic approach to the analysis of grammatical phenomenon, we describe the expression of one and the same grammatical form expressing different causal meanings in different contexts proceeding from the position they are used (**when, where, who, how, why**) in the course of communication between interlocutors.

The verbs with the zero morpheme **uxlaØ** "sleep" (in Uzbek imperative form of the verb is expressed by the zero morpheme), **o'qi** "read" become non-causative forms only when they are opposed to the causative forms **uxlat** and **o'qit**.

Mentioned above verbs 1) **uxla** "sleep" and **o'qi** "read" being opposed to **uxladi** "slept" – **uxlayapti** "is sleeping" – **uxlaydi** "will sleep"; 2) **o'qi** "read" being

Active Voice	Reflexive Voice	Reciprocal Voice	Passive Voice
yuv-di "he washed (something)"	yuvin-di "he washed (himself)"	yuvish-di "they washed (something)"	yuvil-di "(something) was washed"

Analysis of the given above examples shows that the definite grammatical meaning expressed by zero morpheme in the structure of the Uzbek language is depended on the position of its usage, that is what form of the word of the same class it is opposed to. F.F. Fortunatov, A.I. Smirnitsky, M.V. Panov and other followers of Moscow linguistic school proceeded from the interpretation that the word is always grammatically formulated and its meaning is not the simple sum of meanings of its morphemes, but a phraseological unit taken together. English word structure also is divided into main and formal parts, for example, in the words **tables**, **benches** we find two parts: 1) **table** -, **bench**-, 2) - **s**, - **es**. Most of the English words such as **a book**, **a pen**, **a chair** coincides with the Uzbek words **bola**, **kitob**, **qalam** where the root and formulated independent word coincide formally. Linguistic analysis of these words shows that these words which are similar to their roots are divided into the main and formal parts. The formal part is expressed implicitly that is by the zero morpheme. The zero morpheme's grammatical meaning is defined on the basis of the binary opposition with the other form of this word, for example:

1) writeØ (Present Simple)→wrote (Past Simple);

writeØ (Active Voice)→is written (Passive Voice);

opposed to **o'qidi** "read [red]" – **o'qiyapti** "is reading" – **o'qiydi** "will read" are considered to be not non-causative forms, but imperative forms of the verbs. Without mentioned oppositions we cannot speak of one or the other form either.

In the pair of verbs **bezamoq/bezatmoq** – "to decorate/to decorate" we find expression of causal meaning with the absence of non-causal meaning. Pair of verbs **bezamoq/bezatmoq** cannot be included in the system of causativization, because only sound distinctions do not make up the form of the word. In the given above pair of verbs **bezamoq/bezatmoq** the same meaning is expressed, that is "to decorate", as we see there is no opposition non-causative/causative concerning form and meaning followed with function.

As we have marked above, imperative form of the mood in Uzbek is expressed by the zero morpheme and it correlates with the causative and indicative forms of the verb depended on the position of its usage.

Analyzing the nature of zero morphemes S. Yakhontov says that, as a rule, agglutinated affixal morpheme is opposed not only to other affixal morphemes, but it is opposed to the zero morpheme as well [32, p. 95]. For example, oblique case forms are opposed to the nominative case form which is expressed implicitly, that is by the zero morpheme; the noun in plural with the affixal morpheme **-lar**: **bolalar** is opposed to the noun in singular which is expressed by the zero morpheme: **bolaØ/bolalar**. The form of the Active Voice of the verb with the zero morpheme is opposed to all other forms of the voice of the same verb.

writeØ (Indicative Mood)→(You) write (Imperative Mood).

2) boyØ (singular)→boys (plural);

boyØ (common case)→boy's (genitive case).

In the Uzbek language we find the same characteristic feature of the word structure:

kitobØ (singular)→**kitoblar** (plural);

kitobØ (common case)→**kitobning** (genitive case).

As we see the grammatical meaning expressed by the zero morpheme in the English and Uzbek word structure is depended on the position it is used, that is, it depends on the binary opposition of at least two or more forms of this word with the same lexical meaning and the same class of words it is included.

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